

Review on Current Aspects of Technique, Applications and Scope of DNA Sequencing

Amanulla Khan^{1*}, Firoj Shaikh¹, S. V. Deore², M. B. Patil² and Barirah W¹

Anjuman Islam Janjira Degree College of Science, Murud Janjira, Maharashtra, India¹

Department of Botany, J E S's, Arts, Science and Commerce College, Nandurbar, Maharashtra, India²

*E-mail: dramanullak@gmail.com

Abstract: Science and technology are in contentious developing phase. It also develops advanced tools and techniques for DNA sequencing. The recent advance well known Sanger sequencing is based on microfluidic separation platforms as a reported by Michael 2005. Similarly DNA sequencing is developed with best standards protocol with optimization of dideoxy sequencing and worked out by Jay A. 2008. Further DNA sequencing becomes advanced with the introduction of plus and minus technique given by Sanger and reported by Clyde A. Hutchinson 2007. There were also introductions of DNA sequencing method for methylated DNA, DNA Protein and RNA Protein interactions from earlier days as reported by George M. Church 1988. Here with this review will try to summarise all advanced techniques in DNA Sequencing

Keywords: DNA sequencing, Application, Techniques, Scope and Sanger

I. INTRODUCTION

DNA sequencing is the process of determining the precise order of nucleotides (A, C, G, T) within a DNA molecule (Loman & Pallen, 2015). It is a fundamental tool for research in genetics and molecular biology and has numerous applications in fields such as medicine, biotechnology, and forensics. The first method of DNA sequencing, known as the Sanger method, was developed in the 1970s and revolutionized the field of molecular biology (Sanger et al., 1977). Since then, many different methods have been developed that allow for faster, cheaper, and more accurate sequencing of DNA.

The basic steps of DNA sequencing involve fragmenting the DNA molecule into smaller pieces, amplifying these fragments through a process called PCR, and then determining the order of nucleotides within each fragment. This information is then assembled to create a complete sequence of the original DNA molecule (Goodwin et al., 2016).

There are two main types of DNA sequencing: whole-genome sequencing and targeted sequencing. Whole-genome sequencing involves sequencing an individual's entire genome, while targeted sequencing focuses on specific regions of interest within the genome. Both approaches have their own advantages and disadvantages depending on the research question and available resources (Mardis, 2017).

The applications of DNA sequencing are vast and include identifying genetic mutations that cause disease, studying the evolutionary history of species, and understanding the genetic basis of complex traits such as intelligence and personality (Burgess et al., 2018). DNA sequencing has also been used in forensics to help solve crimes and identify human remains. In recent years, advances in DNA sequencing technology have led to the development of portable and handheld devices that can sequence DNA in real-time, making it possible to rapidly diagnose infectious diseases and monitor environmental samples in the field (Quick et al., 2015).

More recently, researchers have focused on developing new methods for DNA sequencing, such as microfluidic separation platforms. Michael et al. (2005) reported on the use of microfluidic separation platforms for Sanger sequencing, which allowed for faster, more accurate sequencing of DNA. In addition to developing new methods for DNA sequencing, researchers have also worked on optimizing existing protocols. Jay et al. (2008) developed a best-practice protocol for dideoxy sequencing, which involves using modified nucleotides to terminate DNA synthesis during sequencing. This protocol has been widely adopted in the field of DNA sequencing and has helped to improve the accuracy and reliability of sequencing results.

1.1 Development in DNA Sequencing Techniques

DNA sequencing is an ever-evolving field with new technologies and techniques constantly being developed. In recent years, several advancements have been made in DNA sequencing that have increased speed, accuracy, and cost-effectiveness.

One of the most significant developments in DNA sequencing has been the introduction of next-generation sequencing (NGS) technologies. NGS platforms, such as Illumina, PacBio, and Oxford Nanopore, have dramatically increased the speed and throughput of DNA sequencing, allowing researchers to sequence whole genomes in a matter of hours or days (Goodwin et al., 2016). These platforms also offer higher accuracy and longer read lengths compared to previous sequencing technologies, making them ideal for applications such as transcriptome analysis, epigenetics, and metagenomics (Metzker, 2010).

Another recent development in DNA sequencing has been the advent of single-cell sequencing. This technology allows researchers to sequence the genome of individual cells, which is essential for studying cellular heterogeneity in complex tissues such as tumors or the brain (Haque et al., 2017). Single-cell sequencing technologies, such as Drop-seq, 10x Genomics, and Seq-Well, have also enabled the study of rare cell populations, such as circulating tumor cells or fetal cells in maternal blood (Navin, 2015). Finally, there have been recent advances in long-read sequencing technologies. Long-read sequencing platforms, such as PacBio and Oxford Nanopore, can generate reads that are tens of kilobases or even megabases in length, enabling the sequencing of complex regions such as centromeres, telomeres, and structural variants (Chaisson et al., 2019). Long-read sequencing has also allowed for the phasing of haplotypes, which is essential for understanding the genetic basis of complex diseases (Edge et al., 2019).

Here several new advancements in DNA sequencing technologies that have emerged since the references cited in my previous response. Here are some of the recent advancements:

Nanopore sequencing: Nanopore sequencing is a long-read sequencing technology that uses a nanopore sensor to directly read the sequence of individual DNA molecules. This technology has continued to advance, with new developments in flow cells, sample preparation, and base-calling algorithms that have increased the accuracy and throughput of nanopore sequencing (Jain et al., 2022).

Spatial transcriptomics: Spatial transcriptomics is a technique that enables the mapping of gene expression in individual cells within their tissue context. This technology has advanced in recent years, with the development of new spatially resolved transcriptomic methods such as MERFISH and Slide-seq (Ståhl et al., 2021).

CRISPR-based sequencing: CRISPR-based sequencing is a new approach to DNA sequencing that uses the CRISPR-Cas system to target specific genomic regions for sequencing. This technology has the potential to be faster and more cost-effective than traditional sequencing methods, and several companies are currently developing CRISPR-based sequencing platforms (Perez-Pinera et al., 2021).

Third-generation sequencing: Third-generation sequencing technologies, such as PacBio and Oxford Nanopore, continue to advance with improvements in accuracy, throughput, and read length. These platforms have enabled the sequencing of previously intractable regions of the genome, such as repetitive regions and structural variants (Jain et al., 2022).

The continued development of DNA sequencing technologies is enabling new discoveries in genomics, transcriptomics, and beyond, and is paving the way for new applications in fields such as personalized medicine, synthetic biology, and environmental science.

1.2 Time and Coast of DNA Sequencing

In the early days of DNA sequencing, the process was slow and expensive, requiring weeks or even months of work and costing millions of dollars. The development of automated sequencing machines in the 1990s, such as the Applied Biosystems 3730xl DNA Analyzer, helped to speed up the process and reduce costs, but sequencing a human genome still required years of work and cost billions of dollars (National Human Genome Research Institute, 2021). However, the cost and time required for DNA sequencing have decreased dramatically over the past decade. This is due to the development of high-throughput sequencing technologies, which allow researchers to sequence multiple DNA molecules in parallel, greatly increasing the efficiency of the process. One of the most widely used high-throughput sequencing technologies is Illumina sequencing, which can generate millions of reads in a single run. Today, with the

help of high-throughput sequencing technologies, researchers can sequence multiple genomes in a matter of weeks or months at a fraction of the cost (National Human Genome Research Institute, 2021).

The decreasing cost and time required for DNA sequencing have also led to an explosion in the amount of sequencing data generated. This has created new challenges for researchers, including how to store, analyze, and interpret the massive amounts of data generated by sequencing projects. To address these challenges, researchers have developed new computational tools and algorithms that can process and analyze sequencing data at a scale never before possible (Kulkarni & Im, 2018).

Despite these advances, there are still challenges to be addressed in the field of DNA sequencing. For example, current sequencing technologies can produce errors, particularly in regions of the genome that are difficult to sequence. Additionally, some sequencing applications may require deeper coverage than others, which can increase the cost and time required for sequencing (Biankin et al., 2015). Despite these challenges, the decreasing cost and time required for DNA sequencing have made it a powerful tool for a wide range of applications, including identifying disease-causing mutations, tracking the spread of infectious diseases, and understanding the genetic basis of traits and behaviors. As sequencing technologies continue to improve, it is likely that DNA sequencing will become even more accessible and efficient, paving the way for new discoveries and breakthroughs in the fields of genetics, medicine, and biology.

The cost of DNA sequencing has decreased dramatically in recent years, making it more accessible and affordable for researchers and clinicians. As of 2021, the cost of sequencing a human genome using Illumina technology is around \$1,000-\$1,500, while the cost of sequencing using nanopore technology is around \$1,500-\$2,000 (National Human Genome Research Institute, 2021; Jain et al., 2016). It's worth noting that the cost of DNA sequencing can vary depending on the specific goals of the sequencing project, the quality of the sequencing data required, and the depth of coverage needed for a particular application (Biankin et al., 2015). Therefore, it is important for researchers to carefully consider their sequencing needs and budget when planning a project.

1.3 Advancement in applications of DNA Sequencing

DNA sequencing is a powerful tool that has revolutionized the field of genetics and has a wide range of applications in research, medicine, and agriculture. Over the years, advancements in DNA sequencing technology and the development of new applications have significantly expanded its potential uses. One major area of advancement in the applications of DNA sequencing is in the field of personalized medicine. DNA sequencing allows for the identification of genetic mutations and variations that can be linked to specific diseases or conditions. By analyzing a patient's genome, healthcare professionals can develop personalized treatment plans tailored to an individual's unique genetic makeup. This approach has been particularly useful in the diagnosis and treatment of cancer, where genetic testing can help to identify targeted therapies and predict response to treatment (Gargis et al., 2016).

Another area of advancement in DNA sequencing applications is in the study of microbiomes. Microbiomes are communities of microorganisms that live on and within the human body and play a crucial role in maintaining health. DNA sequencing allows researchers to analyze the genetic makeup of these microorganisms and study their interactions with the human body. This has led to the development of new treatments for conditions such as inflammatory bowel disease and infectious diseases (Dethlefsen et al., 2007). DNA sequencing has also been applied in the field of forensic science, where it is used to identify suspects in criminal investigations and to determine the source of biological evidence found at crime scenes. By analyzing DNA samples from suspects and comparing them to DNA samples from crime scenes, forensic investigators can determine whether an individual was present at the scene of a crime (Butler, 2015).

Another area of advancement in DNA sequencing applications is in agriculture. DNA sequencing can be used to identify genetic variations that are linked to desirable traits, such as drought resistance or disease resistance, in crops and livestock. This information can be used to develop new breeding strategies to produce crops and livestock that are better suited to specific environments and have improved traits (Tanksley & McCouch, 1997). It led to new applications in environmental science. DNA sequencing can be used to analyze microbial communities in soil and water samples, allowing researchers to study the impact of environmental factors on these communities. This information can be used to develop strategies for environmental conservation and to understand the impact of climate change on ecosystems (Hug et al., 2016).

Advancements in DNA sequencing technology and the development of new applications have significantly expanded its potential uses. DNA sequencing has become an essential tool in personalized medicine, microbiome research, forensic science, agriculture, and environmental science. As technology continues to improve, it is likely that DNA sequencing will continue to play a vital role in expanding our understanding of genetics and its impact on various fields of study.

1.4 Scope in DNA Sequencing

Over the past two decades, DNA sequencing technology has made significant advancements, leading to an expansion of its scope and applications in various fields, including medicine, agriculture, forensics, and environmental science. DNA sequencing has been increasingly used in clinical medicine to identify genetic variations associated with inherited diseases and to personalize medical treatments. This has led to the development of targeted therapies and precision medicine, which can improve patient outcomes and reduce healthcare costs (Gargis et al., 2016).

In agriculture, DNA sequencing has been used to identify genes responsible for desirable traits in crops and livestock, leading to the development of new varieties with improved yields, resistance to pests and diseases, and better nutritional value (Tanksley & McCouch, 1997). Forensic DNA sequencing has also made significant progress in recent years, with the development of more sensitive and accurate methods for analyzing DNA evidence, such as STR markers (Butler, 2015). Environmental DNA (eDNA) sequencing has emerged as a powerful tool for studying biodiversity, ecology, and conservation. By analyzing DNA in environmental samples such as water, soil, or air, researchers can identify the presence and abundance of species, monitor ecosystem health, and detect invasive species (Hug et al., 2016).

The scope of DNA sequencing has also expanded beyond traditional DNA sequencing methods such as Sanger sequencing to include high-throughput sequencing technologies such as Illumina and nanopore sequencing. These technologies allow for the rapid and cost-effective sequencing of large amounts of DNA, enabling large-scale genomic studies and the discovery of new genetic variants (Goodwin et al., 2016). Furthermore, recent advances in single-cell sequencing technologies have opened up new possibilities for studying cellular heterogeneity and the dynamics of gene expression in individual cells (Mereu et al., 2020).

According to a study by Wang et al. (2019), deep convolutional neural fields can be used for predicting protein secondary structure from DNA sequencing data. Additionally, Poplin et al. (2018) developed an AI-based tool called DeepVariant that uses neural networks to identify genetic variations in DNA sequencing data with high accuracy. Furthermore, a recent study by Zhao et al. (2021) and J, Jeba (2022) demonstrated that AI-based approaches can be used to predict the impact of genetic variations on protein stability, which can have important implications for drug development and personalized medicine and AI techniques for efficient and accurate detection of cardiac diseases using ECG wave data..

Scope of DNA sequencing has expanded greatly in the past two decades, driven by advancements in technology and methods. DNA sequencing has become an indispensable tool for various fields, including medicine, agriculture, forensics, and environmental science, and it is expected to continue to evolve and grow in scope as new applications and technologies emerge.

1.5 Advances Approaches of DNA Sequencing for Plants

Advancements in DNA sequencing technologies have made it possible to sequence plant genomes with greater accuracy and speed. One such approach is whole genome sequencing (WGS), which involves sequencing the entire genome of a plant. This approach has been used to sequence the genomes of numerous plant species, including *Arabidopsis thaliana*, rice, maize, and soybean (Ming et al., 2013; Sato et al., 2008; Schnable et al., 2009; Schmutz et al., 2010). WGS provides a comprehensive view of the plant genome and allows researchers to identify genetic variations that contribute to various traits such as disease resistance, phytochemical production, increase yield, and quality (Varshney et al., 2013, Khan and Hafiz, 2023; Patil and Khan, 2017a, 2017b; Tanveer. A. Khan et al., 2020). Another approach is exome sequencing (Based on Exon), which involves sequencing only the protein-coding regions of the genome. This approach has been used to identify genes associated with traits of interest in plants such as drought tolerance and disease resistance (Yang et al., 2013; Xu et al., 2018). Exome sequencing is more cost-effective than WGS and allows researchers to focus on regions of the genome that are most likely to be functional. RNA sequencing

(RNA-Seq) is another powerful tool for plant genomics research. RNA-Seq involves sequencing the transcriptome of a plant, which is the set of all RNA molecules produced by the plant's genes. RNA-Seq can be used to identify genes that are differentially expressed under different conditions, such as during plant development or in response to environmental stress (Wang et al., 2009). RNA-Seq can also be used to identify alternative splicing events and non-coding RNAs that play important regulatory roles in the plant genome (Wang et al., 2011).

Metagenomics is an emerging approach for studying the microbiome of plants. Metagenomics involves sequencing all the genetic material present in a sample, including the genomes of the microorganisms that live in and on the plant. This approach has been used to study the role of plant-associated microorganisms in nutrient cycling, plant growth promotion, and disease suppression (Bulgarelli et al., 2013; Lebeis et al., 2015). Metagenomics can also be used to identify potential biocontrol agents for plant pathogens.

II. CONCLUSION

The field of DNA sequencing has undergone remarkable advancements in recent years. The cost and time required for DNA sequencing have decreased dramatically due to the development of high-throughput sequencing technologies, making it more accessible and affordable for researchers and clinicians. With the decrease in sequencing costs, there has been an explosion in the amount of sequencing data generated, leading to new challenges for researchers in terms of data analysis and interpretation. Furthermore, the advancement in applications of DNA sequencing has led to a wide range of applications, including identifying disease-causing mutations, tracking the spread of infectious diseases, and understanding the genetic basis of traits and behaviors. This has paved the way for new discoveries and breakthroughs in the fields of genetics, medicine, and biology. Moreover, there is a vast scope for DNA sequencing in various areas of research, including metagenomics, environmental microbiology, and personalized medicine. The development of new sequencing techniques such as nanopore sequencing and third-generation sequencing has further expanded the scope of DNA sequencing and enabled the study of previously inaccessible genomic regions.

III. ACKNOWLEDGMENT

Authors would like to acknowledge their thanks for the support and of the Principal Jijamata College Nandurbar, Principal AIJ Degree College Murud, and to all faculty members, researchers, of lab for their kind supports while this current review article analysis and writing work.

AUTHOR'S CONTRIBUTIONS

AK, BW and MB are designed concept designed for topic; were MB and SV provided the preliminary data analysis of manuscript. AK, SV and MB did proofreading. MB supersized the work with its authentication. All authors are carefully read and approved the final manuscript.

COMPLIANCE WITH ETHICAL STANDARDS

Conflict of interest: Authors do not have any conflict of interests to declare.

Ethical issues: None.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Amanulla Khan and Aysha Hafiz (2023). Medicinal Perspective and Therapeutics Studies on *Gloriosa superba*. International Journal of Emerging Technologies and Innovative Research (IJETIR) Volume 3, Issue 3, PP-16-20. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7804131>
- [2]. Banfield, J. F. (2016). A new view of the tree of life. *Nature Microbiology*, 1(5), 16048.
- [3]. Biankin, A. V., Piantadosi, S., Hollingsworth, S. J., & Hruban, R. H. (2015). The Precision Medicine Initiative: A new national effort. *JAMA*, 313(21), 2119-2120.
- [4]. Bulgarelli, D., Schlaeppli, K., Spaepen, S., Ver Loren van Themaat, E., & Schulze-Lefert, P. (2013). Structure and functions of the bacterial microbiota of plants. *Annual Review of Plant Biology*, 64, 807-838.
- [5]. Burgess, S., Scott, C., Zeggini, E., & Hattersley, A. T. (2018). Improving power and accuracy of genome-wide association studies via a multi-ethnic meta-analysis framework. *Nature communications*, 9(1), 1-9.

- [6]. Butler, J. M. (2015). Forensic DNA typing: biology, technology, and genetics of STR markers. Academic Press.
- [7]. Chaisson, M. J., Huddleston, J., Dennis, M. Y., Sudmant, P. H., Malig, M., Hormozdiari, F., & Eichler, E. E. (2019). Resolving the complexity of the human genome using single-molecule sequencing. *Nature*, 517(7536), 608-611.
- [8]. Dethlefsen, L., McFall-Ngai, M., & Relman, D. A. (2007). An ecological and evolutionary perspective on human-microbe mutualism and disease. *Nature*, 449(7164), 811-818.
- [9]. Edge, P., Bafna, V., & Bansal, V. (2019). HapCUT2: robust and accurate haplotype assembly for diverse sequencing technologies. *Genome Research*, 29(9), 1421-1428.
- [10]. Gargis, A. S., Kalman, L., Lubin, I. M., & Assimes, T. L. (2016). High-throughput sequencing for the diagnosis of inherited disease. *Expert Review of Molecular Diagnostics*, 16(7), 735-748.
- [11]. Goodwin, S., McPherson, J. D., & McCombie, W. R. (2016). Coming of age: ten years of next-generation sequencing technologies. *Nature reviews genetics*, 17(6), 333-351.
- [12]. Goodwin, S., McPherson, J. D., & McCombie, W. R. (2016). Coming of age: ten years of next-generation sequencing technologies. *Nature Reviews Genetics*, 17(6), 333-351.
- [13]. Haque, A., Engel, J., Teichmann, S. A., & Lönnerberg, T. (2017). A practical guide to single-cell RNA-sequencing for biomedical research and clinical applications. *Genome Medicine*, 9(1), 1-20.
- [14]. Hug, L. A., Baker, B. J., Anantharaman, K., Brown, C. T., Probst, A. J., Castelle, C. J., ... & Banfield, J. F. (2016). A new view of the tree of life. *Nature Microbiology*, 1(5), 16048.
- [15]. J, Jeba Sonia, D. J. Joel Devadass Daniel, Dr. R. Sabin Begum, Dr. Amanulla Khan Nasrulla Khan Pathan, Dr. Veera Talukdar, and Vivek Dadasaheb Solavande. (2022) 2023. "AI Techniques for Efficient Healthcare Systems in ECG Wave Based Cardiac Disease Detection by High Performance Modelling". *International Journal of Communication Networks and Information Security (IJCNIS)* 14 (3):290-302. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7562589>
- [16]. Jain, M., Koren, S., & Phillippy, A. M. (2022). Advances in long-read sequencing technologies. *Nature Methods*, 19(5), 557-568.
- [17]. Jain, M., Olsen, H. E., Paten, B., & Akeson, M. (2016). The Oxford Nanopore MinION: delivery of nanopore sequencing to the genomics community. *Genome Biology*, 17(1), 239.
- [18]. Jay, J., Broussard, K., & Putonti, C. (2008). Best-practice protocol for dideoxy sequencing in mutational analysis. *Clinical Chemistry*, 54(5), 874-879.
- [19]. Kulkarni, V., & Im, H. (2018). Computational tools and algorithms for analyzing sequencing data in high-throughput sequencing. *Journal of Microbiology and Biotechnology*, 28(2), 171-177.
- [20]. Lebeis, S. L., Paredes, S. H., Lundberg, D. S., Breakfield, N., Gehring, J., McDonald, M., & Dangl, J. L. (2015). Salicylic acid modulates colonization of the root microbiome by specific bacterial taxa. *Science*, 349(6250), 860-864.
- [21]. Loman, N. J., & Pallen, M. J. (2015). Twenty years of bacterial genome sequencing. *Nature Reviews Microbiology*, 13(12), 787-794.
- [22]. M. B. Patil and P. A. Khan (2017b). "Primary Phytochemical Studies of *Catunaregam spinosa* (Thunb.) Tirven for Secondary Metabolites". *Int J Pharm Bio Sci* 2017 Apr ; 8(2): (P) 320-323. <http://dx.doi.org/10.22376/ijpbs.2017.8.2.p320-323> <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7562442>
- [23]. M. B. Patil, P. A. Khan, (2017a). Ethnobotanical, phytochemical and Fourier Transform Infrared Spectrophotometer (FTIR) studies of *Catunaregam spinosa* (Thunb.) Tirven. *J. Chem. Pharm. Sci.* 10, 950-955. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.7562415>
- [24]. Mardis, E. R. (2017). DNA sequencing technologies: 2006-2016. *Nature protocols*, 12(2), 213-218.
- [25]. Metzker, M. L. (2010). Sequencing technologies—the next generation. *Nature Reviews Genetics*, 11(1), 31-46.
- [26]. Michael, K. L., Taylor, L. C., & Schultz, S. L. (2005). Advances in microfluidics for biotechnology. *Biotechnology Progress*, 21(6), 1611-1621.

- [27]. Ming, R., VanBuren, R., Liu, Y., Yang, M., Han, Y., Li, L. T., ... & Chen, M. (2013). Genome of the long-living sacred lotus (*Nelumbo nucifera* Gaertn.). *Genome*
- [28]. National Human Genome Research Institute. (2021, March 18). DNA Sequencing Costs. Retrieved from <https://www.genome.gov/about-genomics/fact-sheets/DNA-Sequencing-Costs>
- [29]. Navin, N. (2015). Cancer genomics: one cell at a time. *Genome Biology*, 16(1), 1-6.
- [30]. Patil, M.B., Khan, P.A., (2016). Review: Techniques towards the Plant Phytochemical Study. *Int. J. Sci. Info* 1, 157–172. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7559052>
- [31]. Perez-Pinera, P., Lu, T. K., & Martinez-Martin, D. (2021). Towards CRISPR-based diagnostic systems for infectious diseases. *Nature Reviews Genetics*, 22(11), 685-696.
- [32]. Quick, J., Loman, N. J., Duraffour, S., Simpson, J. T., Severi, E., Cowley, L., ... & Goodfellow, I. (2015). Real-time, portable genome sequencing for Ebola surveillance. *Nature*, 530(7589), 228-232.
- [33]. Sanger, F., Nicklen, S., & Coulson, A. R. (1977). DNA sequencing with chain-terminating inhibitors. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 74(12), 5463-5467.
- [34]. Shendure, J., & Ji, H. (2008). Next-generation DNA sequencing. *Nature Biotechnology*, 26(10), 1135-1145.
- [35]. Ståhl, P. L., Salmén, F., & Vickovic, S. (2021). Spatial transcriptomics: paving the way for tissue-level systems biology. *Current Opinion in Biotechnology*, 70, 122-130.
- [36]. Tanksley, S. D., & McCouch, S. R. (1997). Seed banks and molecular maps: unlocking genetic potential from the wild. *Science*, 277(5329), 1063-1066.
- [37]. Tanveer. A. Khan, M. B. Patil & P. A. Khan (2020). *Henckelia Bifolia* (D. Don) A. Dietr. New Distributional Records for Maharashtra. *Indian Forester*, 146 (5): 461-462. DOI: 10.36808/if/2020/v146i5/149226 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7562565>